

People's Salvation Cathedral (Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului)

also known as “National Cathedral (Catedrala Națională)”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Orthodox Christianity, Religious Place, Religious Complex, Cathedral

The People's Salvation Cathedral (Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului) is the main house of worship of the Romanian Orthodox Church. It is located on top of Arsenal Hill, in Bucharest's city centre, surrounded by important state institutions: the Palace of the Parliament eastwards, the Romanian Academy of Sciences south-east and the Ministry of Defence westwards. The cathedral was first conceived in 1881 by King Carol I to celebrate the independence gained against the Ottoman which led to the establishment of the new-born Kingdom of Romania. Following disagreements over the most suitable location, recurrent lack of financing and unfavourable historical events, its realisation was postponed several times until the outbreak of WWII. The project was shelved after Romania became a socialist republic in 1948 and gained again momentum only after its collapse in 1989. Ever since, it took two decades, two different Patriarchs, the benevolent attitude of the whole political spectrum and two ad-hoc laws for construction works to take off. The laying of the foundation stone in 2007 officially started the construction works, which are supposed to end in 2025. The cathedral was consecrated and inaugurated with a week of public celebrations between November and December 2018, on occasion of both St. Andrew's day (the patron saint of Romania, November 25th) and the 100th anniversary of the Great Union declaration of Alba Iulia (December 1st), which led to the formation of the modern Romanian state. Once finished, the cathedral will become the seat of the Romanian Patriarchate and of the Bucharest Archbishopric, whose current leader is Patriarch Daniel Ciobotea. Its alternative name – “national cathedral” – has been adopted by church hierarchs and spokespersons to highlight its civil significance: honouring notable national figures and fallen soldiers by performing funerals and commemorations is, in the eyes of the Patriarch, among the main purposes of this new imposing religious complex. It is 125 meters tall – the highest house of worship in Eastern Christianity – and includes halls, chapels with a crypt, four nuclear shelters, offices and cells, a canteen, a religious articles store, a medical consulting room, a museum of Romanian Orthodox, exhibition rooms, apartments and a council room. When asked about the brand-new cathedral, Patriarch Daniel argued he intended to erect a symbol of national significance, “a Latin-Byzantine basilica, traditional, especially in the interior, but with a Romanian taste, a point of connection between East and West” (Vasilescu 2010: 538).

Date Range: 1881 CE - 2025 CE

Region: Bucharest, Romania

Region tags: Romania

The location of the People's Salvation Cathedral. Currently under construction, it will serve as the patriarchal cathedral of the Romanian Orthodox Church.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

— — — — —

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Noica, Nicolae. 2010. *Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului: Începutul împlinirilor*. Bucharest: Basilica.
- Source 2: Noica, Nicolae. 2011. *Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului: Istoria unui ideal*. Bucharest: Basilica.
- Source 3: Tateo, Giuseppe. 2020. *Under the Sign of the Cross. The People's Salvation Cathedral and the Church-Building Industry in Postsocialist Romania*. New York-London: Berghahn Books.

Notes: Further sources: Vasilescu, Gheorghe. 2010. 'Noua Catedrală Patriarhală - Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului. Documentar istoric', in Aa. Vv., *Autocefalia: libertate și demnitate*. Vol. I. Bucharest: Basilica, pp. 493-539.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://catedrala-nationala.ro/>
- Source 1 Description: The official website of the People's Salvation Cathedral
- Source 2 URL: <https://pictamcatedrala.ro/>
- Source 2 Description: The official website of the People's Salvation Cathedral, with a focus on paintings and decorations.
- Source 3 URL: <https://patriarhia.ro/>
- Source 3 Description: The official website of the Romanian Patriarchate

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

Type of elevation

- Hill

Notes: It is customary in Orthodoxy that houses of worship are on elevated terrain and oriented eastwards.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

Notes: In an effort to destroy the historic centre of Bucharest and establish a new communist capital, Ceaușescu bulldozed the area where the national cathedral is now standing to erect the "House of the People", today the "Palace of the Parliament". Broad boulevards and high buildings replaced the pre-modernist grid of the Uranus, Rahova, and Izvor neighbourhoods, an urban fabric made up of little streets and a lot of low-rise residences and villas. In the 2000s, the urban planners and architects working on the project considered the empty plot of land on Arsenal Hill to be the most suitable location: not only it was already cleared up, but the soil composition also seemed to be perfect for construction purposes (Tateo 2020: 37).

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: A wall divides the religious complex from boulevards, Arsenal Square and the residential areas located southwards. The same wall secludes the Palace of the Parliament from the rest of the urban fabric: however, the Cathedral and the Palace are distant only a few hundred meters and are not separated from one another.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The religious complex stands only a few hundred meters away from Union Square and the Old Town, being located in the southwestern part of the city centre. It is surrounded by the Palace of the Parliament, the Ministry of Defence and the Romanian Academy of Sciences

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Religious Complex constructed on bare land.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Religious complex is structured as follows: the main building is the cathedral situated at the centre, surrounded by portics and two buildings dedicated to St. Apostle John and St. Apostle Paul. The former will host the Holy Synod of the Romanian Orthodox Church, the latter the "Basilica" press agency.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: The relevance of this religious complex cannot be reduced to sole worship purposes. As the church is a 'human-divine institution' (așezământ divino-uman) started by Christ and composed by the lay and the clergy, its significance is at the same time spiritual, social, memorial and political. The brand-new cathedral is supposed to commemorate the national heroes that fought for the land, thus adding the specifically secular cult of the nation to liturgical and devotional purposes. Lastly, the sacrament of communion is also an allegory of the sacrifice of Christ: far from a simple symbolical reference, the sacrificial element is part and parcel of the Divine Liturgy and in homiletics.

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The construction is brand-new. However, among the reasons set forth by the Romanian Patriarchate, there is the commemoration of those churches torn down in the area between 1977 and 1989.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Like any other consecrated house of worship, the cathedral is place for worshipping and communicating not just with the Lord and the Holy Trinity, but also with the Virgin Mary and the Saints.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: Unless one follows the nationalist metaphor according to which an ethnic nation can be understood as an extended kinship diagram. "The celebration of state funerals and the creation of pantheons, crypts and mausoleums within brand-new religious complexes ensure continuity in national genealogies and aim at transforming historically situated political systems into

natural entities blessed by divine intervention. National cathedrals are thus monuments celebrating the unity between the religion of the majority, the state and national belonging through the lens of kinship metaphors: not only do the living understand national figures as forefathers – as if they were ascendants – but they are also concerned with the yet-unborn as future members of the nation" (Tateo 2021: 38).

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: The project was commissioned by the Romanian Patriarchate and funded by both private donations and public financing. Law 261/2005 guaranteed the constant financial support of the state and granted for free the plot of land where the cathedral is being built. The Church is the owner of both the religious complex and the respective plot of land of 11 hectares.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: Two important construction firms were the main contractors: Bogart (underground works) and Strabag (works on the surface). They in turn hired several subcontractors to acquire more or less qualified local workforce.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: The causal chain shows rather the opposite: Christian cathedrals have often been built in history as a thanksgiving to decisive divine interventions in important historical events. This is the case for Christ the Savior Cathedral in Moscow (victory over the French invader in the early 19th century); the Temple of Divine Providence in Warsaw (celebration of Poland's first constitution in 1791); the Main Cathedral of the Russian Armed Forces (75th anniversary of the victory in the great patriotic war in 1945). Likewise, the People's Salvation Cathedral was first conceived to celebrate the military victory against the Ottoman Empire and the consequent establishment of the Kingdom of Romania.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Notes: 1877/1878 Independence war won against the Ottoman Empire

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: As of 2018, the construction costs of the religious complex were about 118 million Euro. Approximately the same amount of money was granted by state authorities (from national, regional and local budgets) to the Church to support the construction works between 2009 and 2018. The amount of private donations has never been made public by the Church. Almost the whole parliamentary spectrum doesn't just declare itself Christian-Orthodox, but is also sympathetic towards the Orthodox Church and willing to obtain its endorsement to gain legitimacy and electoral support.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Notes: Namely, the favourable intervention in the victorious independence war of 1877-1878.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Notes: The only relevant landscape feature is the hill on which the cathedral is being built: not because it is of any particular relevance, but because building on an elevated surface (like the top of a hill) is in accordance with the Orthodox tradition.

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The religious complex is composed of: a main building (the national cathedral), two smaller buildings located north-east and south-east, and portics surrounding the cathedral.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main building is the cathedral at the center of the religious complex

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Until the establishment of the contemporary nation-state, the majestic magnitude of cathedrals had been alien to Romania's Orthodox visual culture for centuries. There are notable variations in the number of buildings of worship and their internal elements even within the Orthodox world. For instance, the usage of higher iconostases - which originate from the Russian Orthodox tradition - were used in Romanian churches and cathedrals only after the nineteenth century.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 6.5

Notes: The surface of the cathedral is 0.72 hectares while the whole plot of land where the religious complex is located is 11 hectares.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 7200

Notes: A few hundred metres from the House of the People, a hefty symbol of Ceaușescu's state atheism, the construction of the world's tallest Orthodox cathedral epitomises the postsocialist cultural transformation in Romania and reveals startling continuities in the use of nationalist rhetoric, a visual index devoted to gigantism, and the liberal use of public resources.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 125

Notes: Official sources report 120 or 125 mt depending on whether the cross on top of the dome is counted or not.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: The walls of the cathedral are made of brick-faced ferroconcrete. The bells and cupolas are in copper, while marbled pavements will enrich the interior of the cathedral.

Notes: "Bucharest lies on a seismic hazard zone. In order to make it as earthquake-proof as possible, the walls of the edifice are multi-layered: two different kinds of bricks have been used for the external layers. The one facing the interior of the cathedral is a surface more apt for paintings, while the exterior one is a thicker kind of brick". (Tateo 2020: 66).

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Only some external decorations have been finalised, like the coppered cover of the cupolas. The painting of the walls (in white, according to the model) should be executed within 2025.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The pavement of the cathedral is marbled while the iconostasis and the walls are decorated with mosaics.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

Notes: Unless one includes the furniture and sacred objects that can be found in an Orthodox house of worship: seats (high-armed chairs called "stacidia"), reliquaries, icons etc.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction,

etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Father, Son, and Holy Spirit are all three equally and undividedly one God, according to Eastern Orthodox Christians. Three separate, divine individuals, each of whom has a single divine essence, make up the Trinity. Only the Son is depicted.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, archangels Micheal and Gabriel are part of the common iconography of Eastern Orthodox Churches and are portrayed in Bucharest's National Cathedral as well.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The iconography includes the Virgin Mary and many saints that are important in the Romanian Orthodox tradition and in Eastern Orthodoxy (St. Dimitrie, St. Parascheva, St. Paisie Aghioritul).

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are often part of Eastern Christian iconography. While paintings and mosaics have not been finalised yet, decorations on the altar portray a sacrificial lamb (an allegory of the redemption of sins). It is likely that other animals often part of Christian iconographies like dragons (as in St. George's icon) and snakes (symbol of satan and thus depicted as trampled down) will be portrayed as well.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Paintings and mosaics have not been finalised yet. When frescoes portray scenes like the Last Judgment, anthropomorphic devils are portrayed as torturing sinners. In Romanian Orthodoxy, the rules regarding the craft of church painting are called "erminii". The most famous treatise for Byzantine painting in Romania was written by the hieromonk Dionysius of Furna (17th-18th centuries).

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No other non-figural decoration is present

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: Eastern Orthodox Churches separate the sanctuary (where the altar is) from the nave and the narthex through an iconostasis. Icons and decorations in the sanctuary are thus only partially visible.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: The Seventh Ecumenical Council (8th Century AD) declared that bidimensional iconography, whether painted or mosaic, was preferable. This would also permit relief iconography, which has a long history of undisputed use in Orthodoxy. Ever since, in many Eastern Orthodox countries statues wouldn't find any place within the church's walls and would be considered instead characteristic of Western Christianity.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

Notes: "Initially we conceived it [the iconostasis] with marble frames for each icon, which is a typical solution in the Orthodox world. Yet, given the size of the iconostasis, the usage of marble made the structure extremely heavy. Patriarch Daniel came one day to me to stop the works and [to propose] a sudden change: to make the iconostasis in mosaic. His idea was to create a single image which was continuous, uninterrupted [unlike the marbled version]. . . " (Interview with Daniel Codrescu, icon painter at the national cathedral. Quoted from Tateo 2020: 70)

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Notes: The decoration of the interior walls of the cathedral will be in mosaic. White paint will decorate the external walls.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

Notes: The main justification for choosing mosaic is its durability. Patriarch Daniel requested engineers to design a cathedral that might survive a thousand years, therefore he is particularly worried about the structure's longevity. Because mosaic is more resilient than frescoes, the Patriarch could have chosen it. The adoption of mosaic is an allusion to Byzantine and Paleochristian art. The famous mosaics of the Rotunda of Thessaloniki's - which date back to the fifth century - were acknowledged as an important influence by the leading icon painter, Daniel Codrescu.

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Father, Son, and Holy Spirit are all three equally and undividedly one God, according to Eastern Orthodox Christians. Three separate, divine individuals, each of whom has a single divine essence, make up the Trinity. Only the Son (Christ) is depicted.

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: "According to the iconographic plan, the mosaics of the cathedral will illustrate scenes taken from the Old and New Testaments, allegorical figures, events from the life of the Savior, the Holy Virgin Mary, the Holy Apostle Andrew, the Protector of Romania and other saints who, through their representation, will restore the foundation historian of the Orthodox Church, so the iconography of the cathedral will include: • The church of the apostolic age, rendered by the representation of the 12 Apostles • The Church of the Patristic Era, of the Holy Fathers of the Greek, Syriac, Latin and Slavic Churches • The Romanian Orthodox Church, ancient and contemporary. Due to the Latin character of Romanian Orthodoxy - emphasized by the great theologian Rev. Prof. Acad. Dr. Dumitru Stăniloae, who notes the fact that the Romanian people are on the one hand Latin, on the other hand, raised in the spirituality of the Holy Fathers of the Church, aspects which distinguish us from an identity point of view both from the Westerners and from the peoples of the East and which give birth to a unitary spirituality that defines the existence of our nation. The saints to be painted in the National Cathedral are not purely random, behind the choice is an extensive documentation process carried out with the help of Mineiului, a church book in which the religious services are indicated, by months and days, through which the lives are presented and the spiritual zeal of the saints, information that serves for a pictorial rendering as deep and as close

to their holy life as possible" (www.pictamcatedrala.ro/concepticonografic).

↳ **Abstract mosaics:**

– Yes

Notes: Non-figural, geometric decorations are present.

↳ **Other [Specify]**

–Other [specify]: With a 400 m² surface and more than 4 million mosaic tesserae, the iconostasis of the national cathedral is the largest in the whole world. The materials for the icons hail from Venice and Carrara.

↳ **Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:**

– Yes

↳ **Are the inscriptions ornamental:**

– No

↳ **Are the inscriptions informative/declarative**

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions haven't been realised yet, and neither it is clear where they will be located. However, according to the leading icon painter, there is a plan to place an inscription to honour the donors.

↳ **Are the inscription a formal dedication:**

– Yes

Notes: The two arched porticos will guard the access to the main entrance to the Cathedral, the one from Strada Izvor, on the west side of the Cathedral. They will join on the line that represents the central axis of the edifice and will have two domes inscribed with messages of gratitude. "One of eternal gratitude to the heroes of the nation, to whom this cathedral is dedicated, and will be written in large, golden letters, as a living gratitude, forever, to their supreme sacrifice for country and faith. The other text will be one of gratitude to all the people who helped in the construction of the cathedral", explained Father Nicolae Crîngaşu. (Source: <https://catedrala-nationala.ro/la-catedrala-nationala-se-va-ajunge-trecand-prin-doua-porticuri-unul-ii-omagiaza-pe-eroi-celalalt-pe-donatori/>)

↳ **Other [Specify]**

–Other [specify]: No other inscription is present

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Stained glass decorates the windows, cupolas are covered in copper, pavements are marbled. Further details on the decoration of the other two buildings surrounding the cathedral have not been revealed yet

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels - who are anthropomorphic but have wings - are portrayed.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Notes: It is customary in Orthodox Christian iconography to represent the Holy Spirit through allegories: as a dove, tongues of fire or bright cloud.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: The last judgment is often present in the iconographic plan - as is the case with the national cathedral.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: As it is customary in the iconographic plan of Orthodox churches, the main scenes of the life of Christ are depicted as well in the interior of the cathedral. The iconographic plan includes events from both the old and the new testament, and combines human and

supernatural narratives.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No other distinct features are present

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: The official plan of the cathedral reports the construction of crypts underground.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: Like in any other Christian house of worship, the commemoration of the dead performed by churchgoers and the clergy is among the most important social and spiritual functions.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Notes: The new cathedral in Bucharest seeks to honour Romanian soldiers and national heroes. The focus was changed from the notion of salvation to that of national affiliation by changing

the name of the building to "national cathedral". Once the cathedral is complete, two significant holidays – the Romanian national day (1 December) and Ascension Day – will be used annually to honour all-time national heroes. In fact, the Parliament passed a law in 1995 mandating that national heroes be honoured on the same day as the Feast of the Ascension.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: With the exception of Justinian Marina (buried in the Radu Voda Monastery), the Patriarchs of the Romanian Orthodox Church have been buried in the patriarchal cathedral ever since the interment of the first Patriarch, Miron Cristea, in 1939. Before he passes away, the current Patriarch Daniel Ciobotea wants the cathedral to be completed as he wants to be the first patriarch to be buried there.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

– Other [specify]: No other treatment

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No other former burial present

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The first council of Nicaea (AD 325) proclaimed that Christ was real God but at the same

time real human, as was incarnate and became man. A theologically-informed approach would thus argue that it is not the Father, nor Christ to be anthropomorphic but quite the opposite: it is mankind to be rather done in the image and likeness of God.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Notes: In the history of Orthodox Christianity, Byzantine Emperor Justinian I (482-565) is famous for having established the principle of *symphonia*, which required the priesthood and the imperial authority to work in harmony and support one another. This famous differentiation between temporal and religious power does not exclude the recurrent adoption of "political" metaphors in relation to god: from the "heavenly kingdom" to the most important depiction of Christ in Orthodox iconography, "Christ Pantocrator" (Greek: Χριστὸς Παντοκράτωρ, literally ruler of all).

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: No other specific remark

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Communication and interaction with God can happen through human (clerics) and non-human (sacred objects) channels.

Notes: From a strictly theological point of view, divine grace is not transmitted by simple contact: the Holy Spirit, rather, goes where believers demonstrate devotion through faith and prayer. The same applies to another mediator of divine grace: the icon. Just like priests, icons are mediators between God and the faithful through grace: as soon as they are blessed, they are matter full of har. According to Orthodox theology, what actually makes miracles is the 'prototype', that is, the saint or holy figure that is made visible through the icon and not the object itself (Lossky and Ouspensky 1999). Yet, just like there are charismatic figures that stand out among the clerics, there are icons that are more venerated than others. The saints, martyrs, Christ, or the Virgin Mary are all the object of veneration by means of icons. (Tateo 2022: 77-78).

Reference: Tateo, Giuseppe. "The Orthodox Charismatic Gift". *The Cambridge Journal of Anthropology* 40, no. 1 (March 1, 2022). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3167/cja.2022.400106>.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The prayers for the dead during the Divine Liturgy is the customary mean of interaction between the dead and the alive.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No other means of communication

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Divine grace ("har" in Romanian) can be experienced as substance-like, as an 'energy'

mediated by ordained priests, charismatic figures and sacred objects (icons, relics).

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Spirit - the third Person of the Holy Trinity - is the means of communication with the living par excellence and is celebrated on the day of Pentecost.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: no other means of communication

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: On the condition that angels are considered "mixed human-divine beings".

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No other means of communication involved

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: No other supernatural monitoring

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Beyond usual money offerings, donors can contribute by buying and donating furniture (seats, chandeliers etc.). On a more general basis, construction firms that are involved in church-building activities have sometimes donated construction materials.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Although rather a form of immaterial offering, expertise can be offered by professionals as a donation to the Church. Take the case of a Bucharest-based attorney who defended the Romanian Orthodox Church pro bono when legal litigations with contractors arose during the construction of the national cathedral.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: It is certainly true that the third commandment asks believers to "keep festivities holy". Nevertheless, church attendance varies significantly among Christian denominations. According to the 2008 European Values Survey, church attendance in Romania is low, with Catholic nations such as Poland, Italy, and Ireland taking the top spots. Attending the major feasts of the liturgical year, fasting before Easter, and participating in pilgrimages are considered more essential in Orthodoxy than regular church attendance, if the latter conceals a sense of restriction and obligation rather than

a genuine desire to go to church. An Orthodox believer is frequently advised not to feel obligated to attend church simply because she is a member of the religious community: 'We should not feel like slaves!' (Să nu ne simțim slugi!), the parish priest of the Biserica Rusa church (Bucharest) used to repeat (quoting St Neagoe Basarab) during a weekly meeting organized for university students. (See also Tateo 2020: 138)

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No other specific remark about maintenance

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– No

Notes: However, the chapel of the cathedral is led by a charismatic priest - Father Gradinaru - who is popular among the faithful for his alleged gift of foresight. Hundreds of believers throng the chapel on a daily basis to get blessed or receive advice from Father Gradinaru.

Do rituals occur at this place:
Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.
– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

Notes: Namely, the celebration of important religious feasts like Easter and funerary rites for important personalities and dead soldiers. State funerals, as well as the establishment of pantheons, crypts, and mausoleums within brand-new religious complexes, assure continuity in national lineages and try to turn historically placed political regimes into natural entities sanctified by divine intervention.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

Notes: For logistic reasons, they are supposed to take place in the underground chapel or in the chapel outside the cathedral (Paraclisul Catedralei, led by archimandrite Ciprian Gradinaru)

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: At the only public event organized so far - the inauguration and consecration of the

cathedral - over 150,000 people from all over the country visited the religious complex during the six days it was open (Data provided by the press agency of the Romanian Orthodox Church)

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: The scheduling of rituals is regulated in the liturgical calendar: beyond the usual weekly celebrations (Divine Liturgy, hymns and prayers, vespers) priests perform life-cycle rituals and blessings that vary in frequency.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: "Discrepancies between popular practice and 'orthopraxis' can emerge in relation to the use of sacred objects. (...) Nevertheless, as is aptly theorized by theologian Vladimir Lossky, differences between orthopraxis and folk praxis are not really conflicting but rather belong to two different traditions, one 'vertical tradition', concerning the god's truth and thus not prone to modifications, and the other 'horizontal', which stands for how the word is understood, expressed and transmitted by humankind (Lossky and Ouspensky [1952] 1999)." (Tateo 2020: 53)

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers and chants performed in unison by the faithful and religious ministers or by the choir in the kliros can be understood as synchronic practices.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

Notes: The Patriarch's residence is located on Metropolitan Hill, a few kilometres eastwards.

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: There are both monks and nuns in Eastern Orthodoxy, but the latter cannot say mass and lead religious functions. There are no nuns in this religious complex: all the religious specialists serving here are male.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: The great majority is Romanian-born.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: Bishops, priests, and deacons comprise the clergy. Archbishops, metropolitans, and the patriarch are all administrative posts recruited from the ranks of monks and expected to be celibate. Furthermore, clergymen are classified based on their work, with priests and deacons classified as 'secular,' as opposed to monks.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: The access to the sanctuary (behind the iconostasis, where the altar is located) is reserved for the religious ministers performing the Divine Liturgy or any other ritual (sacraments, hymns and prayers etc.)

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Cells for monks and bishops have been built in the religious complex.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: It is yet unclear whether the cathedral will be adopted for celebrating the ordination of the clergy.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: The bureaucratization of religion was described in the 1960s by Peter Berger (1967: 139–40) as a sign of internal secularization which characterizes Christian churches in manifold ways: Internally, the religious institutions are not only administered bureaucratically, but their day-to-day operations are dominated by the typical problems and 'logic' of bureaucracy. Externally, the religious institutions deal with other social institutions as well as with each other through the typical forms of bureaucratic interaction. 'Public relations' with the consumer clientele, 'lobbying' with the government, 'fund raising' with both government and private agencies, multifaceted involvements with the secular economy (particularly through investment). In all these aspects of their 'mission', the religious institutions are compelled to seek 'results' by methods that are, of necessity, very similar to those employed by other bureaucratic structures with similar problems. Many of the activities described by Berger are carried out by the ROC as well: lobbying and fundraising with state and private agencies – the promulgation of laws favouring the ROC like Law 261/2005 being the most apparent example – as well as investing in sectors not always related to religious purposes. As dioceses are allowed to own companies and make profits for self-support, it has become common practice for the ROC to invest in the real estate business, the agricultural sector, faith tourism and the construction industry. The Metropolitanate of Moldova, for example, is the owner of hotels, construction firms, printing houses, agricultural firms that have contributed to produce almost three million Lei of surplus to be redistributed in the budget of the following year. Making profits to reinvest is crucial to expand pastoral activities. Since the quota for clerical salary state contributions is fixed, if the ROC wants to set up new parishes and raise the number of priests it is obliged to pay them their salary from its own funds. Lastly, the strengthening of media services falls within the same category and represents one of the most important achievements of Patriarch Daniel. (Tateo 2020: 152).

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: Article 2 of Law 261/2005 transferred the plot of land where the religious complex is currently being built to from state property to the Romanian Patriarchate. The value of this plot of land was esteemed to be of 200 million Euros.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: The Romanian Orthodox Church is among the 18 state-recognized religions and, as such, is considered by law a 'public utility organization'. It is supposed to cover civil functions such as celebrating funerals of important personalities and Romanian soldiers.

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– I don't know

Notes: In the early 2010s, some unofficial construction plans of the religious complex mentioned the realisation of a soup kitchen. However, information released by the Romanian Patriarchate in recent years has never hinted at a kitchen soup, neither this is present in the plans illustrated in the official website (catedrala-nationala.ro).

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No other public function involved.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: People's Salvation Cathedral (Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului), Tateo, Giuseppe. *Under the Sign of the Cross*. Berghahn Books, 2020.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Under_the_Sign_of_the_Cross.html?hl=&id=pBbSDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: People's Salvation Cathedral (Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului), Tateo, Giuseppe. "New Cathedrals in Postsocialist Europe: Turning Chance into Destiny". In *Politics of Religion: Authority, Creativity, Conflict*, edited by Alessandro Testa. Munster: LIT Verlag, 2021.

Reference: People's Salvation Cathedral (Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului), Stan, Lavinia, and Lucian Turcescu. *Religion and Politics in Post-communist Romania*. OUP USA, 2007.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Religion_and_Politics_in_Post_Communist.html?hl=&id=15YRDAAAQBAJ.

Reference: People's Salvation Cathedral (Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului), Leustean, Lucian N.. *Eastern Christianity and Politics in the Twenty-first Century*. Routledge, 2014.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=zt2vAwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: People's Salvation Cathedral (Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului), Noica, Nicolae. "Catedrala Mântuirii Neamului. Inceputul Implinirilor", January 1, 2010.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Other [specify]: Communication and interaction with God can happen through human (clerics) and non-human (sacred objects) channels., Tateo, Giuseppe. "The Orthodox Charismatic Gift". *The Cambridge Journal of Anthropology* 40, no. 1 (March 1, 2022).

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3167/cja.2022.400106>.